

Assessment of Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness among Pregnant Mothers Attending Ante Natal Care Service in Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital, South West Ethiopia

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Abstract

Background: Every pregnancy is risk of having life-threatening obstetric complications. A birth preparedness package promotes active preparation and assists in decision-making for healthcare seeking in case of such complication. Although its importance is fact, it is low in Ethiopia.

Objective: To assess how pregnant women in Mizan Tepi University Teaching Hospital prepare for delivery and in the occurrence of complication practice and its associated factors, southwest Ethiopia.

Method: A facility based cross sectional study was conducted in antenatal clinic of Mizan Tepi University Teaching Hospital on a sample of 392 pregnant women in 2016. Data was collected using pre-tested structured questionnaire which was adapted from previous similar studies. Data was collected, checked and reviewed on daily basis by supervisors. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 21 software. Bivariate analyses was done to identify factors associated with birth preparedness and complication readiness and those found significant (p -value ≤ 0.25) were entered in the multivariate logistic regression analysis. The results were presented in frequency table, odds ratio and 95% confidence interval.

Results: Of the sample mothers, 392 making response rates of 98.7% were successfully interviewed. Among these, 51% of them were identified place for their recent birth while almost half of them 49% were not identified place for their recent birth. Majority of women 77.6% were heard about birth preparedness and complication Readiness. High proportions were got information from health professionals 75.8%. Among the factors considered for birth preparedness and Complication Readiness were lower monthly income, maternal and husband education, maternal occupation showed statistically significant association.

Conclusion: The magnitude of birth preparedness and complication readiness was moderate in the study area. Preparedness in health system, ensuring competence, and motivations of workers are needed for promoting BPCR among the study population.

Keywords: Antenatal care; Birth preparedness; Complication readiness; Knowledge

Background

Birth preparedness and complication (BP/CR) readiness is the course of action of planning for normal birth and anticipating the action needed in the case of emergency [1-3]. It is also an approach to promote utilization of skilled maternal and neonatal care timely, based on the assumption that preparing for child birth and being ready for complications reduces delay in obtaining this care [4-7].

Birth-preparedness and complication-readiness is a comprehensive package aimed at promoting timely access to skilled maternal and neonatal services. The birth preparedness package promotes active preparation and decision-making for delivery by pregnant women and

their families. This emerged from the fact that a pregnant woman faces risk of sudden and unpredictable life threatening complications that could end in death or injury to herself or to her infant [3,7-10]. This is because complications such as hemorrhage are unpredictable and highly fatal if timely treatment is not obtained. The package of BPCR is a very important strategy in developing countries, where obstetric services are poor. There is also enough evidences from Nepal, Burkina Faso and India that promoting BPCR improves preventive behaviours, improves knowledge of mothers about danger-signs, and leads to improvement in care-seeking during obstetric emergency therefore reducing disability and death associated with child birth [11-13].

Unfortunately the utilization of skilled birth attendant is low even in settings where services are accessible. For past times maternal deaths are thought to occur due to three delays: delay in deciding to seek appropriate care; delay in reaching an appropriate health facility; and

delay in receiving adequate emergency care once at a facility. In many societies in the world, cultural beliefs and lack of awareness inhibit preparation in advance for delivery of the expected baby. Since no action is taken prior to the delivery, the family tries to act only when labour begins [12-15]. The majority of pregnant women and their families do not know how to recognize the danger signs of complications. When complications occur, the unprepared family will waste a great deal of time in recognizing the problem, getting organized, getting money, finding transport and reaching the appropriate referral facility [4,5,12,13]. In Ethiopia; only 42% of pregnancies are unintended and more than half a million pregnancies are ended, More than 25,000 women died due to pregnancy and childbirth complications each year nationally and of the total (553) maternal deaths in the facilities, 74% are caused by direct while 26% are caused by indirect obstetric complication [16-18].

Despite the birth preparedness and complication readiness strategy was aimed to improve awareness of women about danger signs of pregnancy related complication and further importance of maternal and neonatal health services, limited information is documented about the practice of birth preparedness and complication readiness among recently delivered mother and associated factors in south west Ethiopia particularly in the study area. Therefore, this study aims to assess practice of birth preparedness and complication readiness among ANC attendant pregnant women in Mizan-Tepi University teaching hospital, southwest Ethiopia.

Methods and Material

Study area and period

The study was conducted in Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital located in Bench Maji zone, south west Ethiopia from March 25 to April 25, 2016. Bench-Maji Zone with capital of Mizan-Aman town, Aman sub town kebele 02 and landed on 97,560 m². It is serving about two million people who live in Bench-Maji, Sheka, Kaffa zones and four districts of Gambela region that demarked the Zone.

The Hospital provides emergency and regular OPD service, Inpatient treatment and care, minor and major surgery, MCH, gynecology and obstetrics, laboratory, radiology, pharmacy, psychiatry, ophthalmic, VCT and ART services. On the other hand the hospital is serving as a teaching hospital by cooperating with Jimma University Specialized and Teaching Hospital and Mizan-Aman Health Science College.

Study design

The facility based descriptive cross-sectional was used.

Source of population

ANC service attendant pregnant women in Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital were the source population.

Study population

The study population was pregnant mothers who were ANC attendants during study period that means in actual study were the study population.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria: Pregnant women on visits of ANC who were willing to be included during interview.

Exclusion criteria: Mothers who were seriously ill or unable to communicate were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size is calculated using a formula for estimation of single population proportion 389 women were taken as sample based on 95% Confidence interval and 5% margin of error, 16% proportion of birth preparedness and complication readiness among women in Jimma Zone 23.3% [16].

By adding 5% non-response rate, which is 19 and the final Sample size was 397.

Sampling procedure/Technique

A systematic random sampling technique was employed to select the study subjects. The sample size was proportionally allocated to the selected health facilities using the two months average client flow. The sampling interval was calculated to be $(K=n/N)$.

Data collection instrument and method

The data collection tool was adapted from JHPIEGO: Maternal and Neonatal Health on monitoring birth preparedness and complication readiness. The adapted questionnaire was modified and contextualized to fit the local situation and the research objective. The questionnaire was prepared first in English, translated into Amharic, and then back into English by fluent speakers of both languages to check its consistency. Data on socio-demographic factors, obstetric factors, and knowledge and practice regarding birth preparedness and complication readiness were collected using a pre-tested and structured questionnaire. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews after training both data collectors and supervisors. The pre-testing was conducted in 5% of the sample size of pregnant mother in Mizan Health Center. After review of the instruments all suggested revisions were made before being administered in the actual study.

Two data collectors and one supervisor were recruited to participate in the study. The selection criteria for data collectors were those individual who had Diploma in nursing. The supervisors have Bachelor degree in public health or nursing and have previous experiences.

Data quality assurance

Training was given for data collectors for three days to ensure the completeness and consistency of information during data collection. The questionnaire was pre-tested before data collection. The investigators and supervisors was checked before receiving the filled questionnaire from each data collector and there was meeting at the end of data collecting time to discuss for improvement.

Data processing and analysis

On each days of data collection, all data collectors checked the data for its completeness and missing information at each point. The collected data was reviewed, coded, entered and analyzed using SPSS software version 16. And the analyzed data was presented by frequency and percentage and by tables.

Back ground variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Age of the mother	15-19	44	11.2
	20-29	272	69.4
	30-39	66	16.8
	≥ 40	10	2.6
	Total	392	100
Marital status	Single	6	1.5
	Married	376	96
	Divorced	2	0.5
	Widowed	8	2
	Total	392	100
Women's educational status	Unable to read and write	144	36.7
	Able to read and write	162	41.3
	Primary education	28	7.7
	Secondary education	30	7.1
	Tertiary education	28	7.1
	Total	392	100
Religion	Orthodox	134	34.2
	Protestant	202	51.5
	Muslim	54	13.8
	Other	2	0.5
	Total	392	100
Ethnicity	Bench	192	49
	Kaffa	69	17.6
	Amhara	69	17.6
	Oromo	42	10.7
	Others	20	5.1
	Total	392	100
Family size	<four	238	60.7
	≥ four	154	39.3
	Total	392	100
Mothers occupation	Private worker	86	21.9
	Government worker	50	12.8
	House wife	184	46.9
	farmers	60	15.3
	Others	12	3.1
	Total	392	100

Mothers income	<200	200	51
	200-500	111	28.3
	500-1000	29	7.4
	>1000	52	13.3
	Total	392	100
Number of children	≤ 3 children	56	14.3
	>3 children	336	85.7
	Total	392	100

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents in In Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital, South West Ethiopia, 2016.

Back ground variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Identified place for your recent birth	No	192	49
	Yes	200	51
	Total	392	100
Identified skilled birth attendant	No	109	27.8
	Yes	283	72.2
	Total	392	100
Saved money	No	288	73.5
	Yes	104	26.5
	Total	392	100
Identified means of transport to place of delivery	No	151	38.5
	Yes	241	61.5
	Total	392	100
Identified blood donor	No	331	84.4
	Yes	61	15.6
	Total	392	100

Table 2: Birth Preparedness and Complication Readiness components in among pregnant mothers in Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital, South West Ethiopia, 2016.

Ethical Consideration

Approval was obtained from the Mizan-Tepi university department Of Public Health. Permission letters was obtained from Mizan-Tepi University. Informed oral consent was obtained from the participant after a comprehensive explanation of the purpose and procedure.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

A total of 392 study subjects were participated in the study making response rates of 98.7%. The majority of women age fall in 20-29 years age group 272 (69.4%). Among the total respondents almost all, 376

(96%) were married while the rest 4% were single, divorced and divorced. Most of the respondents, 202 (51.5%) were protestants by Orthodox religion 134 (34.2%). Regarding educational background, majority of women were able to read (had no formal education)

followed by unable to read in their educational status were 162 (41.3%) and 144 (36.7%) respectively. Concerning ethnicity majority were Bench 192 (49%), Kaffa and Amhara comprises equal proportion with 162 (17.6%) followed by Oromo 42 (10.7%) (Table 1).

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Heard about BP/CR	No	88	22.4
	Yes	304	77.6
	Total	392	100
Source of information to know about BP/CR	Your mother	14	3.6
	Married media	30	7.7
	Health professionals	297	75.8
	Your friends	51	13
	Total	392	100
Any previous serious health problems related to the pregnancy?	No	364	92.9
	Yes	28	7.1
	Total	392	100
What problems did you experienced?	Vaginal bleeding	24	6.1
	Swollen hands/face	2	0.5
	Blurred vision	2	0.5
	Total	28	7.1
Danger signs those endanger the life of a pregnant woman?	Vaginal bleeding	277	70.7
	Swollen hands/face	61	15.6
	Blurred vision	54	13.8
	Total	392	100
Danger signs during labor and childbirth that can endanger the life of a pregnant woman?	Severe vaginal bleeding	208	53.1
	Prolonged labor (>12hours)	102	26
	Convulsion	40	10.2
	Retained placenta	42	10.7
	Total	392	100
Danger signs during the first 2 days after birth that could endanger the life of the woman?	Severe vaginal bleeding	233	59.4
	Foul-smelling vaginal discharge	108	27.6
	High fever	51	13
	Total	392	100
Danger signs the first 7 days after birth that could endanger the life of a newborn baby?	Difficult or fast breathing	61	15.6
	Yellow skin/eye color (jaundice)	16	4.1
	Poor sucking or feeding	219	55.9
	Plus, bleeding, or discharge from around the umbilical cord	16	4.1

	Baby very small	50	12.8
	Convulsions/spasms/rigidity	2	0.5
	Lethargy/unconsciousness	28	7.1
	Total	392	100
What are the basic care that can be provided to a newborn baby immediately after birth?	Exclusive breastfeeding	296	75.5
	Dry and wrap eye	32	8.2
	Cord care	64	16.3
	Total	392	100

Table 3: Maternal Knowledge on key danger sign of pregnancy, labour and post partum in Mizan-Tepi University Teaching Hospital, South West Ethiopia, 2016.

Birth preparedness and complication readiness components in among pregnant mothers

Among the total study participants, 200 (51%) of them were identified place for their recent birth while almost half of them 192 (49%) were not identified place for their recent birth. Majority of respondents 283 (72.2%) identified skilled birth attendant while only 109 (27.8%) of them were not identified skilled birth attendant for their birth. The least number of respondents were saved money and identified blood donors for their birth with having 104 (26.5%) and 61 (15.6%) respectively.

In general 161 (41.1%) of mothers have practice of BPCR (Table 2).

Maternal knowledge on key danger sign of pregnancy, labour and post partum

Majority of women 304 (77.6%) were heard about Preparedness and Complication Readiness. High proportions were got information from health professionals 297 (75.8%). Few mothers were encountered serious health problem in their recent previous pregnancy about 28 (7%). among the problems hemorrhage comprises 24 (85.7%) (Table 3).

Maternal birth preparedness and complication readiness and associated factors

Maternal birth preparedness and complication readiness was associated with their monthly income, education, still birth and saving money were variables independently affecting BP/CR while other variables were controlled for possible confounding variables.

Those mothers who have monthly income 500-1000 Ethiopian birr per month were five times more likely prepared for birth and ready for complication than bellow 200 birr per month with AOR=4.8, at 95% CI (2.1, 11.4) with p value <0.05. Other income categories were also more likely prepared for birth and ready for complication.

Other variable is maternal education in which mothers who were able to read and write were two times more likely prepared for birth and ready for complication than unable to read and write with AOR=1.9, at 95% CI (1.1, 3.4) with p value <0.05. Also saving money is associated with Maternal birth preparedness and complication readiness by which mothers who saved money were less likely better than their counter parts with AOR=0.35, at 95% CI (0.2, 0.56) with p

value <0.01. Mothers whom had no still birth were less likely better than their counter parts with AOR=0.4, at 95% CI (0.12, 0.91) with p value <0.01 (Table 4).

Discussion

This study was conducted to assess prevalence of birth preparedness and complication readiness its associated factors among mothers in south western Ethiopia.

The finding of this study revealed the prevalence of birth preparedness and complication readiness was 41.1%. It implies for the need of both community and facility-level interventions to improve maternal survival and the importance of quality ANC interventions to increase BPCR practice in the setup. This finding is higher than the study conducted in Ghana, Nepal, Bale robe Ethiopia and India [1], Adigrat 22% [19] and Robe Oromiaregion 16.5% [15]. This difference may be due to MDGs implementation and difference in the study setting.

Maternal education has significant effect on BPCR. This result is in line with the studies conducted in other parts of Ghana, Eretria, Robe, Nigeria [12,15,20,21]. This might be due to the fact that knowledge and awareness towards maternal and child health will be increased as the education level increases.

In the current study both mother and husband occupation were not significant factors of BP CR. This is inconsistent with studies done in Uganda and Nigeria [22]. The difference could be impact of the government's free provision of ambulance service, medical supply and other services for maternal and child health during birth.

In this study pregnant women who had no history of still birth were negatively determined BPCR practice. This might be due to those pregnant women could predict serious complications from their previous experiences as similar study done in Ethiopia [18].

In this study those pregnant women who have saved money were less likely to be prepared for birth and its complication than those who didn't save money. This finding is not in line with the previous studies done in Tanzania, Uganda and Dire Dawa city in Ethiopia [15,13,20,23-26]. This might indicate that delivery charge free service for maternal and child care are being valuable and societies are utilizing well.

In our findings health information and education has no effect on BP and CR. This is not similar with others studies [27-30]. This may implies that most of our study area mothers come from pastoral and semi pastoral rural areas.

Variables	Practice of BP/CR			
	Yes	No	COR (95% C.I)	AOR (95% C.I)
Women's educational status				
Unable to read and write	94	50	1	
Able to read and write	20	10	3.4 (1.923, 5.958)*	1.9 (1.1, 3.4)*
Primary education	24	4	3.1 (1.049, 9.71)*	1.5 (0.6, 4.5)
Secondary education	140	22	1.064 (0.462, 2.447)	2.1 (0.7, 5.9)
Tertiary education	26	2	6.9 (1.576,30.333)	3 (0.9, 10)
Husband education				
Unable to read and write	12	35	1	1
Able to read and write	24	44	1.4 (0.76, 2.5)	0.4 (0.43, 1.6)
Primary education	63	84	0.6 (0.28, 1.4)	0.4 (0.17, 1.1)
Secondary education	46	60	1.4 (0.75, 2.6)	0.6 (0.25, 1.2)
Tertiary education	16	8	3.6 (1.4, 9.8)*	0.8 (0.25, 3.1)
Mothers income				
<200	140	60	1	
200-500	21	8	2.5 (1.383, 4.683)*	3.6 (2.1, 6.2)*
500-1000	95	16	1.1 (0.472, 2.682)	4.8 (2.1, 11.4)*
≥ 1000	48	4	5.1 (1.775, 14.902)*	3.6 (1.4, 8.9)*
Still birth				
Yes	18	10	1	1
No	143	22	0.36 (0.16, 0.8)*	0.4 (0.12, 0.91)*
Saved money				
Yes	61	43	0.4 (0.24, 0.6)**	0.35 (0.2, 0.56)**
No	100	18	1	

Table 4: Association of socio-demographic characteristics and practice maternal birth preparedness and complication readiness among ANC attendants in MTUTH south West Ethiopia, 2016.

Conclusion

Our study showed that below half of pregnant women were well prepared for delivery and obstetric complication, but majority of pregnant women planned to deliver at home. Beyond this little proportion of pregnant women identified blood donor and transportation.

Our study showed maternal education, monthly income, history of past obstetric complications and saving money were factors affect

BPCR independently. This is similar with study done in Malawi [31]. For this reason health Information and Education should be provided for every mothers of reproductive age regardless of an educational status and monthly income on birth preparedness and complication readiness early. The government officials, executives, stakeholders and partners that are working in areas of maternal health should develop scientific approaches to advance birth preparedness at individual, household and community level.

Competing Interests

We declare that we have no competing interests exist.

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